

SEMΔCRET project and UNFC resource mapping of selected CRM in Europe

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CZECH
GEOLOGICAL
SURVEY

SEMCRET Project

- Sustainable exploration for orthomagmatic (critical) raw materials in the EU:
Charting the road to the green energy transition
- **HORIZON CL4 2021 RESILIENCE 01-06** - Innovation for responsible EU sourcing of primary raw materials, the foundation of the Green Deal (RIA)
- **1 June 2022 – 31 May 2025**
- **16 project partners**, led by University of Oulu (Finland)
- **Objective:** Enhancing exploration of orthomagmatic deposits (Ni, Cu, Co, PGE, Cr, Ti, V)
- React to expected sharp increase of demand with green energy transition

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HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-06

UK Research and Innovation

What it is about?

- The aim is to increase prospectivity in Europe
- Exploration methods refining – „Mineral System Approach“
- Multi-expertise cooperation – economic geologists, geochemists, geophysicist, machine learning experts, biologists, social scientists, geoinformatics, etc.

Work packages:

- WP1** – Refining the ore deposit model for orthomagmatic deposit types (metal source, metal pathway, metal sink)
- WP2** – Regional-scale exploration, definition of proxies and prospectivity modelling applicable in exploration
- WP3** – Brownfield exploration – geochemistry, geophysics, litho-geochemical modelling and machine learning on 5 reference sites
- WP4** – Social awareness (stakeholder, community analysis, rising awareness, policy recommendation)
- WP5** – Mineral resources mapping, UNFC conversion
- WP6** – Dissemination, clustering, communication, exploitation

5 reference sites:

- Lapland (Finland)
- Suwalki (Poland)
- Sleza (Poland)
- Ransko (Czechia)
- Beja complex (Portugal)

Figure 3: Translating Mineral Systems Approach to large regional scale exploration (SEMCRET Project GA No. 101057741)

Figure 1: Distribution of different types of orthomagmatic ore deposits in EU (SEMCRET Project GA No. 101057741)

Figure 2: Multidisciplinary approach illustration (SEMCRET Project GA No. 101057741)

WP5 – Mineral resource mapping

- Resource mapping of orthomagmatic rocks related to exploration and exploitation potential of selected (critical) raw materials Ni, Cu, Co, PGE, Ti, V, Cr

Task 5.1

- Survey of primary and secondary mineral potential of exploration and production-related orthomagmatic mineral systems (deposits, prospects and occurrences)
- Main focus are European countries + Greenland
- Database development and feeding (sources: existing DTB, research papers, reports, etc.)
- GIS visualization will be produced

Figure 4: Graphical presentation of the SEMACRET project components and their interrelation (SEMACRET Project GA No. 101057741)

UNFC Task within the SEMACRET Project

Task 5.2 – conversion to UNFC based on the data collected within the task 5.1

- UNFC conversion in line with existing documents and guidances (UNFC update 2019, UNFC Guidance Europe 2022, CRIRSCO-UNFC Bridging Document – updated version), etc.
- Selected projects in different stages will be chosen as a „Case studies“ for a detailed conversion to UNFC – SEMACRET reference sites + few other exemplary cases,
- Single UNFC class per deposit/project („best UNFC class“) – testing for the objects within the database
- Work in progress - Report (Deliverable D5.2) will be provided by the end of 2024

SEMACRET_Ore_measurements_DTB

Project Num	Completed	Project Name	Occurrence ID	Occurrence type	Target commodities	Other materials of economic potential																																																																																																														
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7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Stendalen - Titanium 01	SEM-1GL022	Prospect	Co; Cu; PGE; Ti; V	low-grade Ni-Cu-Co mineralisation is present and widely distributed the intrusion. Moreover, it has PGE potential to be explored.																																																																																																														
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Resources ID</th> <th>Commodity</th> <th>Ore measurement type</th> <th>Ore amount</th> <th>uomweight</th> <th>Best UNFC</th> <th>UNFC class</th> <th>Commodity grade</th> <th>Unit</th> <th>Commodity amount</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>titanium</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>0 t</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>0 %</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>*</td> <td>(Nové)</td> <td>Proven reserves</td> <td>Pr-rv</td> <td>111</td> <td></td> <td>If historical estimate, then 221</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Probable reserves</td> <td>Pb-rv</td> <td>112</td> <td></td> <td>If historical estimate, then 222</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Measured resources</td> <td>Ms-rs</td> <td>221</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Indicated resources</td> <td>Id-rs</td> <td>222</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Inferred resources</td> <td>If-rs</td> <td>223</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Exploration results</td> <td>Ex-rt</td> <td>334</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Non-compliant resource</td> <td>N-com</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Choose relevant UNFC class</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Total endowment</td> <td>T-edw</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Total (geological) resources</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Additional quantity</td> <td>Ad-q</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Choose relevant UNFC class(es)</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							Resources ID	Commodity	Ore measurement type	Ore amount	uomweight	Best UNFC	UNFC class	Commodity grade	Unit	Commodity amount	7	titanium			0 t			0 %			*	(Nové)	Proven reserves	Pr-rv	111		If historical estimate, then 221						Probable reserves	Pb-rv	112		If historical estimate, then 222						Measured resources	Ms-rs	221								Indicated resources	Id-rs	222								Inferred resources	If-rs	223								Exploration results	Ex-rt	334								Non-compliant resource	N-com			Choose relevant UNFC class						Total endowment	T-edw			Total (geological) resources						Additional quantity	Ad-q			Choose relevant UNFC class(es)			
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8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Skaergaard				GE (Au-Pd dominant) mineralization, including also Ag and PGE content calculated as average PdEq without Au = 155 ppm based on the MRE (2012); NI43-101 (indicated 2.2,3): 81,6 Mt @ 42 g/t V, 13 g/t TiO2																																																																																																														
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Ikertog (Ni)				made of all mineralised samples is 2% Ni, 0.33% Cu and 0																																																																																																														
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Ryberg (Miki Fjord)	SEM-1GL023	Prospect	Co; Cu; Ni; not-listed; Pd; Pt; PGE	Gold mineral potential as well																																																																																																														

Figure 5: Illustration of preliminary version of SEMACRET database in MS Access (B. Wertichová 2024)

Thank You

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#SustainableExplorationEU

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